

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ALI****FIRST NAME: ABDIAZIZ****PROGRAM CODE: DIDOL****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The student applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics
 The student used Turabian/ Chicago parenthetical/in-text references.
 The author did use Zotero to insert references
 The student did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)
 My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%
 The writer used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 10)

List of 5 key concepts with page numbers

1. The Notion of essay writing (EUCLID 2021,6-12)
2. Academic writing fundamental rules (EUCLID 2021,15-24)
3. Comparison of US & UK English (EUCLID 2021,24-32)
4. The concept of plagiarism in academic writing (EUCLID 2021, 33-36)
5. Forms of abbreviations in academic writing (EULID 2021,56-62)

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ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have gone through the ACA-401D course and its materials, including [course pack](#) and [video](#), which I have received. During my reading, this subject is critical to understanding the requirements of academic writing and communicating with others correctly. Accordingly, I have learned the underlying essay writing guidelines and their steps, punctuation rules, and regulations. Then, the differences between American and British English, the concept of plagiarism and its negative impact on academic writing, why we need to apply one unique style in our academic writing, and how the abbreviations can be correct.

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Learning outcomes of this course will be helpful for the upcoming classes and the rest of my life in academics and beyond.

To understand more, I will discuss the notion of essay writing. Then I will examine academic writing rules and compare American and British English. Furthermore, I will explain quickly the concept of plagiarism and how it can be avoided, along with the correct

forms of abbreviations in academic writing. Finally, I will end my response paper with a terse conclusion that represents the summary of this paper.

2) THE NOTION OF ESSAY WRITING

Essay writing in literary form is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic writing. Examples of academic writing include research findings or reports on empirical fieldwork, translation, technical, or conference paper (EUCLID 2021, 7).

Essay writing has such common steps to be followed and applied obligatory. Notably, they are to search for the topic, organize their ideas, start writing essays, reference the article, edit the paper and hand it in (EUCLID 2021,7–12).

The academic writing process is to search for the appropriate topic to be studied. After defining what your issue is about, you need to gather enough information in regard whith this particular task. Followed by organizing the information, ideas, and resources you have collected.

Once that step is done, the essay writer plans how he can sensitize the information he collected. The writing plan also involves ordering information in a logical scientific argumentative order.

In essay writing, you must consider the sentences and the paragraph you will use. The subtitles your essay may contain without forgetting to include the introduction, the body, and the conclusion to ensure the effectiveness of your essay writing (EUCLID 2012, 10).

3) ACADEMIC WRITING FUNDAMENTAL RULES

Scholarly writing can only take place by applying strict rules and procedures. The most common rules of academic writing are punctuation. Every punctuation type has unique marks and exclusive usage. Using punctuation marks in academic writing will directly affect the meaning of words, sentences, and the structure of the essay at large.

According to the given materials by Euclid, there are so many inevitable punctuations in academic writing, including; Apostrophe, brackets, bullet points, colons and semicolons, commas, dashes, a hyphen, full stops, exclamation marks, question, and quotation marks (EUCLID 2021,16–23).

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4) COMPARISON BETWEEN US & UK ENGLISH

America and British constitute the two dominant countries in English accents. However, they are not hosting native speakers alone, but we have several countries that speak English as a native (mother tongue).

Earlier in World War II, the British English accent was superior. Nevertheless, almost everything dramatically changed, and the US dominated the market, including language, culture, technology, money, media, and so on (EUCLID 2021, 25).

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The US and the British have more similarities than differences, especially in the scientific field. However, they also have widespread variants that require awareness at all speaking, writing, reading, and listening levels. The most common variants between those two countries can appear in pronunciation, spelling, grammar, some meanings of words, phrases, vocabularies, punctuations, terminologies, and others (EUCLID 2021,25–32).

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism occurs when a writer fails to acknowledge the source of information in an academic paper. It is a serious academic offense that can cause serious consequences, considered compulsory in academic writing (EUCLID 2021, 34).

To avoid plagiarism (a core feature of academic writing), you must keep up copyrights and originalities of information. Plagiarism avoidance can only happen when you use your own words and your expression while giving others an acknowledgment of the source of information collected.

The outstanding solution to plagiarism is to apply a citation system. The citation mentions the author and the source of information shared. There are two common whys of citation systems, namely, quotations and paraphrases. A quotation is to repeat and use the exact words the author utilized, while a paraphrase is to use an author's ideas and information and write it down with your comments, forms, and structures (EUCLID 2021, 35–37).

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6) FORMS OF ABBREVIATIONS IN ACADEMIC WRITING

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Every singular academic writing has a unique style being applied thoroughly. This consistency requires sentence structure, font style, spelling standards, page layout, heading formats, and many more.

Euclid University prefers the Chicago style over any given and dominant style for writing, such as APA, due to its effectiveness in research papers. Chicago Style is the way of formatting books and documents introduced and originated by the University of Chicago (EUCLID 2021, 44).

In academic writing style, we must be familiar with abbreviations and expressions. Therefore, An acronym is a short form of a word or phrase, made by leaving out some of the letters or using only the first letter of each term. Examples of abbreviations are Dr., e.g., A.M., and Ltd.

7) CONCLUSION

Academic writing requires grasping and complying strictly with specific processes, rules, and regulations; scholarly writing can take place with them. Accordingly, while reading the materials of this course, I was taught effective laws which will benefit the rest of my life. These rules were outlined in above mentioned topics, including the process of easy writing and how it can be effective, the fundamental lows of academic writing, the comparison between UK and US English, plagiarism and how you can avoid it, and the examples of abbreviations in academic writing, all of whom I briefly explained and summarized in the above pages.

It is worth mentioning that during my master's study (12 years back), I used an APA style guidance in writing my thesis. In contrast, I m currently using the Chicago Style. Both are American products, but the APA is commonly used in social science, while the Chicago Style is more suitable in research papers.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

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